

PERFORMANCE OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN AGRICULTURE SECTOR IN NAGPUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

This Research Project presents a comprehensive study of present scenario and usage of digital platforms used by farmers of Nagpur district of Maharashtra. The study aims to examine the operational dynamics, and marketing strategies by the digital platform companies and evaluating their performance by using both quantitative and qualitative methods. The research begins by providing an overview of the performance of digital platforms in agriculture sector and factors influencing productivity and profitability. It further explores the unique usage of digital platforms by farmers and their perception on the digital platforms. The thesis delves into the marketing strategies employed, including direct sales, network-based marketing, and the role of intermediaries in reaching the broader market. It also highlights the challenges faced by the Agri-tech sector in agriculture, such as disease management, price volatility, and market access.

Keywords: Digital Applications; digital platforms; awareness; willingness to participate; quantitative variables; qualitative variables;

Introduction and Objectives

Digital transformation in India has been an ongoing journey, playing a significant role in the modernization of various sectors, including agriculture. The early adoption of information technology in the 1980s set the stage for a nationwide movement toward digitalization, which gained momentum through subsequent decades. With the liberalization reforms of 1991 and the rapid growth of India's IT industry, companies like Infosys and Wipro became prominent global players. This paved the way for significant technological advancements, such as the implementation of Aadhaar in 2008 and the digital governance strategies that followed. The current research builds upon these developments, focusing on the intersection of digital technology and agriculture, particularly in the Nagpur district.

Agriculture, a vital sector in India, has undergone gradual but significant digital transformations over the years. The early introduction of initiatives like AGMARKNET and ITC's e-Choupal system in the late 1990s marked the beginning of a digital shift in farming practices. These efforts aimed to provide farmers with better market information, advisory services, and access to technology. The ongoing evolution of digital agriculture, particularly with the rise of mobile connectivity and agri-tech startups in the 2010s, offers a framework for understanding the role of digital platforms in enhancing agricultural productivity and profitability. This research seeks to explore these dynamics within Nagpur's agricultural landscape, where digital adoption remains crucial for rural development.

The Digital India initiative, launched in 2014, has further accelerated the integration of digital services across various sectors, with agriculture being one of its focal points. The proliferation of platforms like e-NAM and mobile applications tailored to farming needs has empowered farmers by providing real-time market data, weather forecasts, and advisory support. The research will investigate how such platforms have been received by farmers in Nagpur, examining their engagement, challenges, and opportunities. Understanding farmers' perception of digital tools is essential to identify gaps in implementation and areas for improvement.

As India moves towards a more technologically advanced agricultural sector, there is an increasing need for research that focuses on localized impacts. The Nagpur district, known for its agricultural activities, provides a unique setting to study the effectiveness of digital interventions. This research aims to assess how farmers in this region are adapting to digital platforms, exploring factors like access to technology, digital literacy, and overall benefits. Insights from this study could shed

light on broader trends and help tailor solutions that resonate with the local farming community.

In doing so, this study contributes to the broader discourse on digital agricultural platforms and offers evidence-based recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders aiming to optimize the benefits of Digital platforms and similar digital platforms in rural and agricultural settings.

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To study the awareness and adoption of input and output for Digital platforms in Nagpur district
2. To assess the adoption various selling and purchasing digital platforms in Nagpur district
3. To study and compare the various digital platforms by farmers in Nagpur district

3. Materials and Methods

The present investigation was conducted in Nagpur district of Maharashtra during 2023-24 nearby villages of Nagpur was chosen on purpose since they using various digital platforms. The survey included 50 farmers from Nagpur. The respondent for the study was operationally defined as the farmers who using the various digital platforms for various purposes in Nagpur. The primary data were collected personally with the help of Survey schedules; the interviews were conducted in farmer's fields or in their homes through face-to-face contact.

-Variables to estimate the awareness and the adoption of input and output digital platforms in Nagpur district.

1)Demographic: age, gender, educational level, farming experience, house-hold size

2)Technological adoption:

Previous experience with technology, access to smartphones, computers

3) Digital Literacy:

Ability to use digital devices, Familiarity with digital platforms, Comfort with technology

4) Perceived utility: Perceived usefulness of digital platforms for farming activities, expected benefits from using digital platforms, Computability of digital platforms with traditional practices

5) Awareness and Knowledge; Awareness of available digital platforms, Knowledge about the functionalities of digital tools, Information sources influencing awareness.

B) Variables to evaluate the various input(purchasing) and output(selling)digital platforms used by farmers in Nagpur district.

1)Demographic: age, gender, educational level, farming experience, house-hold size

2) Types of platforms used: e-nam, Agrostar, Agribolo,

Mandi Trades, FPO website, Nijacart

3) Perceived benefits: Increase in income, better price, middleman occurrence and price comparison between online and off lines
 4) Market access website : Maharashtra state Agri-cultural websites, state agricultural websites, state agricultural Universities website,

5) User Experience: user Interface design, ease of navigation and reliability of platforms.

⚡ Comparative Variables to estimate the various digital platforms by farmer in Nagpur district.

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Results and Discussion

Farmers awareness towards digital platforms

The pie chart indicates a significant level of awareness among farmers in Nagpur regarding digital platforms, with 90% of respondents reporting familiarity with these technologies. This high percentage suggests that digital platforms are becoming an integral part of agricultural practices in the region, potentially influencing decision-making, market access, and resource management. Conversely, the 10% of farmers who are not aware of digital platforms highlights a gap that may hinder their ability to leverage modern agricultural innovations. This lack of awareness could be attributed to various factors, including limited access to technology, insufficient training, or socio-economic barriers.

Farmers adoption towards digital platforms in Nagpur

The pie chart illustrates that 80% of farmers in Nagpur have adopted digital platforms for their agricultural practices, indicating a strong inclination towards embracing technological advancements. This substantial level of adoption suggests that farmers are recognizing the value of digital tools in enhancing productivity, improving market access, and optimizing resource management. However, the 30% of farmers who have not adopted digital platforms raises a critical concern regarding the barriers they may face in integrating these technologies into their operations. This discrepancy could stem from factors such as a lack of awareness, inadequate infrastructure, or challenges related to training and support.

Farmers adoption toward digital platforms for input (purchasing) in Nagpur

The table data presents an overview of digital platform usage among farmers in the Nagpur district. Out of the total 50 farmers surveyed, Agrostar emerges as the most utilized platform, with 34% of respondents reporting engagement. This indicates a strong preference for Agrostar, likely due to its targeted offerings and accessibility. Following Agrostar, Bharat Agri accounts for 22% of usage, suggesting its significant role in the agricultural digital ecosystem. Other platforms, such as Amazon and Flipkart, attract minimal engagement, with only 10% and 8% respectively, indicating that farmers may be less inclined to use general e-commerce sites for agricultural needs. Notably, 20% of farmers reported not using any digital platform, which highlights a potential gap in digital adoption that could be addressed through targeted outreach and education initiatives. Overall, the data underscores the importance of understanding farmers' preferences and the need for platforms to adapt to their specific requirements.

Farmers adoption towards digital platforms for output (selling) in Nagpur

The data reveals significant insights into digital platform usage among farmers in the surveyed area. Of the 50 farmers, only 14% reported using NAAS Rating – 04.17

Big Basket as a digital platform, highlighting a limited engagement with online grocery services in this demographic. In stark contrast, a substantial 86% of farmers indicated that they do not utilize any digital platforms for their agricultural or grocery needs. This overwhelming majority suggests a pronounced reluctance or inability to engage with digital technologies, which may be influenced by factors such as lack of access, digital literacy, or trust in online services. The findings underscore a critical opportunity for initiatives aimed at increasing digital adoption among farmers, emphasizing the need for education and resources to bridge the gap between traditional practices and digital engagement.

Comparison of various digital platforms used by farmers for different purposes in Nagpur

The above pie chart is showing analysis of digital platform usage among farmers in Nagpur reveals distinct preferences based on the purposes these platforms serve. According to the pie chart data, 20% of farmers primarily utilize weather applications, underscoring the importance of accurate and timely weather information in their agricultural decision-making processes. Additionally, 10% of farmers engage with a variety of platforms, including Agrostar, Bharat Agri, Flipkart, Facebook, WhatsApp, and YouTube, indicating a diverse approach to leveraging digital tools for various agricultural needs and Maha DBT 10%. Meanwhile, only 5% of farmers reported using Agri Bolo and Big Basket, suggesting that these platforms have yet to gain significant traction in this demographic. This distribution of usage highlights the critical role of weather apps in farmers' operations and points to opportunities for enhancing engagement with other digital platforms through targeted outreach and tailored content that addresses the specific needs and interests of the farming community.

Advantages perceived by digital farmers while usage of various Input (purchase) digital platforms Nagpur

The above table provides a comprehensive overview of the advantages perceived by farmers in relation to digital platforms. Among the 50 farmers surveyed, guidance on agrochemical usage was identified as the most significant benefit, with 24% of respondents highlighting its importance. This suggests that farmers are actively seeking support in optimizing their chemical applications for improved crop yields and sustainability. Climate forecasting and expert guidance each received equal acknowledgment from 20% of the farmers, indicating a strong demand for reliable weather information and professional advice to enhance their agricultural practices. Additionally, 10% of farmers cited guidance in seed sowing and weed management, while 6% focused on disease and pest management, reflecting a broader interest in improving crop health and management techniques. Lastly, 10% noted the importance of price machinery, which highlights the relevance of cost considerations in their operational decisions. Overall, the findings emphasize the diverse needs of farmers and the critical role that digital platforms can play in addressing these requirements through targeted solutions and expert support.

Challenges faced by farmers while using various digital platforms in Nagpur

From the above table presents an analysis of the disadvantages perceived by farmers regarding digital platforms. Among the 50 farmers surveyed, a significant majority 74% indicated that they do not experience any disadvantages associated with their use of these platforms. This suggests a generally positive perception of digital tools within the agricultural community. However, for the 26% who reported disadvantages, concerns included the risk of fake products (8%), quality issues (6%), and the possibility of no results from their engagement (6%). Additionally, 4% of farmers cited high prices as a concern, while only 2% noted damage related to their experiences. These findings indicate that while digital platforms are widely accepted, there are important areas for improvement, particularly in ensuring product authenticity and quality.

Addressing these concerns could enhance user trust and further encourage the adoption of digital solutions among farmers.

Constraints faced by farmers while usage of various digital platforms for different purposes in Nagpur

The table outlines the constraints faced by farmers in adopting digital platforms, with a focus on their ranking based on the number of respondents. Digital illiteracy emerges as the most significant constraint, reported by 20 farmers and ranked first, indicating a critical barrier to effectively utilizing digital tools. Following this, language problems were identified by 10 farmers, ranking second, which suggests that language barriers may hinder access to information and services. Lack of awareness about digital platforms ranked third, with 9 respondents acknowledging this issue, emphasizing the need for increased outreach and education initiatives. Interface design concerns were noted by 5 farmers, ranking fourth, indicating that user experience could be a deterrent for some users. Additionally, 3 farmers cited a lack of training as a constraint, ranking fifth, while less land holding and lack of product knowledge were reported by 2 and 1 farmer, respectively, ranking sixth and seventh. These findings highlight the multifaceted challenges that farmers face in adopting digital technologies, underscoring the necessity for targeted interventions that address these specific constraints to facilitate greater engagement with digital platforms.

Farmers Awareness Towards Digital Platforms

Pie chart 01: Farmers awareness towards digital platforms

Farmers Adoption Towards Digital Platforms

Pie chart 02: Farmers adoption towards digital platforms in Nagpur

Table no.01: Farmers adoption toward digital platforms for input (purchasing) in Nagpur

Sr.No	Name of Digital Platform	No of Farmers	In Percentage
1	Agrostar	17	34.00
2	Flipkart	4	8.00
3	Dehatt	3	6.00
4	Bharat Agri	11	22.00
5	Amazon	5	10.00
6	Not using any platform	10	20.00
	Total	50	100.00

Table no 02: Farmers adoption towards digital platforms for output (selling) in Nagpur

Sr. No	Name of Digital Platform	No of Farmers	In Percentage
1	Big Basket	7	14.00
2	No usage of platforms	43	86.00
	Total	50	100.00

Table no 03: Comparison of various digital platforms used by farmers for different purposes in Nagpur

Sr. No	Advantages	No of Farmers	In Percentage
1	Climate Forecast	10	20.00
2	Guidance In Seed Sowing	5	10.00
3	Disease And Pest Management	3	6.00
4	Weed Management	5	10.00
5	Guidance On Agrochemical	12	24.00
6	Expert Guidance	10	20.00
7	Price Machinery	5	10.00
	Total	50	100.00

comparison of various digital platforms used by farmers

Table no 04 : Advantages perceived by digital farmers while usage of various Input (purchase)digital platforms Nagpur

Table no 05: Challenges faced by farmers while using various digital platforms in Nagpur.

Sr. No	Challenges	No of Farmers	In Percentage
1	Fake Product	4	8.00
2	Damage	1	2.00
3	Quality Issues	3	6.00
4	No Results	3	6.00
5	High Price	2	4.00
6	No disadvantages	37	74.00
	Total	50	100.00

Table no 06: Constraints faced by farmers while usage of various digital platforms for different purposes in Nagpur

Sr. No	Name Of Constraints	No of Farmers	Ranking
1	Digital Illiteracy	20	I
2	Language Problem	10	II
3	Lack Of Awareness	9	III
4	Inter Face Design	5	IV
5	Lack Of Training	3	V
6	Less Land Holding	2	VI
7	Lack Of Product Knowledge	1	VII
	Total	50	

Conclusion

The study reveals that digital platform usage among farmers is predominantly observed in the middle-aged group (30-50 years), with 58% of users falling within this age range. Lower-income farmers are more likely to engage with these technologies, as 78% of users report lower incomes. Marginal farmers lead in adoption rates (34%), followed by medium (28%), small (24%), and large farmers (14%). Additionally, 90% of farmers are aware of digital platforms, with 80% having adopted them for agricultural purposes. Agrostar (34%) and Bharat Agri (22%) are the most popular platforms among users. Farmers primarily utilized digital platforms for weather forecasting (20%) and expert guidance, experiencing significant benefits such as improved climate forecasting and support in agricultural practices. However, challenges remain, including digital illiteracy, language barriers, and issues related to product quality and pricing. Addressing these constraints is essential for improving farmer engagement with digital tools and enhancing their overall productivity and market access.

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